

CONDITIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE ABILITIES IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS USING ORIGAMI IN TECHNOLOGY LESSONS

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Abstract. *Educational tools ensure the implementation of a pedagogical technique within a specific educational method. Educational tools also include toys, teaching materials, household items, construction and other materials, tools, laboratory equipment, visual aids, etc. For example, the main tool for developing children's creativity can be their own creative activity and familiarization with the results of the creative work of adults. To implement a creative idea, it is necessary to develop the skills and abilities necessary for this activity. Any development of skills and abilities requires explanation, demonstration, and exercises. In the development of creative activity, an important role is played by the ability to solve creative problems.*

Keywords: *pedagogy, psychology, technology, education, training, primary school, origami lesson, teaching.*

The main requirements for teachers in modern education are to bring the content of education in line with the requirements of modern standards and to create conditions for the creative development of the child. Analysis of regulatory documents shows that in the standard of primary education and in the model programs, the tasks of creative development of students are designated in all educational areas.

In organizing creative activities, it is necessary to be guided by the provision on the need for deep processing of scientific knowledge, its solid assimilation and development of not only thinking, memory of students, but also methods of independent knowledge acquisition. This principle entails the principle of algorithmization used in programmed learning, which assumes the introduction of methods and means of independent knowledge acquisition into training. In accordance with the identified principles, we selected the methods and means of education. I. F. Kharlamov [9] calls the means of education specific forms and types of educational work (classes, various conversations, excursions, etc.), which are used by teachers in the process of applying a particular method.

As A.V. Khutorskoy [15] notes, these tasks are expressed in a general formulation: the ability to solve creative problems at the level of combinations, improvisations: independently draw up an action plan (concept), demonstrate originality in solving a creative problem, create creative works (messages, short essays, graphic works), play out imaginary situations. Target guidelines serve as the basis for us to take into account the successive connections of preschool and primary general education and in the design of pedagogical interaction with children.

In her work, S.V. Kulnevich identifies conditions that are conducive to the development of children's creativity. "Such conditions are: 1. Early physical and intellectual development of children. 2. Creation of an environment that is ahead of the child's development. 3. Independent solution by the child of problems that require maximum effort, when the child reaches the "ceiling"

of his capabilities. 4. Providing the child with freedom in choosing an activity, alternating tasks, duration of classes on one task, etc. 5. Smart, friendly help (not hints) from adults. 6. A comfortable psychological environment, encouragement by adults of the child's desire for creativity" [6, p. 62].

Thus, according to the teacher, properly organized creative activity of a schoolchild increases his involvement in the educational process, promotes successful acquisition of knowledge, stimulates intellectual efforts, self-confidence, and fosters independence of views. From all of the above, it follows that the effective development of creative activity of younger students can be organized in conditions specially created by the teacher. M.N. Skatkin [15] identified the following methods of activating creative activity: problematic presentation of knowledge, discussion, research method, creative work of students, creation of an atmosphere of collective creative activity in the lesson.

If a teacher does not have such a personality trait as a focus on creativity, then he will demand only reproductive level knowledge from his students. The second condition for the development of creative activity, put forward by R.S. Nemov [3] - strives to solve the most difficult tasks for him. It consists in the fact that the activity should be as difficult as possible, but feasible, or, in other words, the activity should be in the zone of potential development of the child. If this condition is met, it is necessary to increase the complexity of creative tasks from time to time. Another important, in our opinion, the third condition for organizing creative activity is the one highlighted by V.A. Levin - the development of creative abilities, which is an integral part of creative activity, and not teaching only technical skills and abilities.

If these conditions are not met, as V.A. Levin emphasized, "many qualities necessary for a creative personality (artistic taste, ability and desire to empathize, desire for something new, sense of beauty) become redundant and unnecessary" [4, p.21]. In organizing the educational process within the framework of our study, it is necessary to take into account two levels of learning – at the reflex and cognitive levels. In the first case, learning can be sensory (informational and cognitive nature of learning), motor (activity-based purposeful nature of learning) and sensory-motor. The second level of learning is associated with the transfer of knowledge, skills and abilities, thinking techniques.

In this regard, special attention should be paid to the content of the student's creative activity. The content of creative activity is understood as two of its forms - external and internal. The external content of education is characterized by the educational environment, the internal is the property of the individual himself, created on the basis of the student's personal experience as a result of his activity. The organization of any form of education and training of children requires a solid scientific basis, and relies on the principles of modern education.

We have analyzed modern educational technologies and consider the model of personality-oriented learning [1] to be the most acceptable for our work with children, since it is within the framework of this model that a democratic style of interaction between a teacher and a child is acceptable, and the teacher himself is an older friend, assistant and advisor for the child. In personality-oriented technologies, the personality of the child is at the center of education, it is the personality, its versatile and creative development that is the main goal of the entire educational system.

The developers of the personality-oriented model (in modern publications – technology) of training (Sh.A. Amonashvili, V.V. Davydov, V.A. Petrovsky and others) believe that "training in joint activities, cooperation of the teacher and children is carried out in conditions when the

students feel their growth, the joy of creativity, improvement” [13, p.220]. It is known that the assimilation of ready-made knowledge does not always bring the expected results. In this statement, we rely on the position of teachers who call for teaching children to independently acquire knowledge, to show initiative in searching for information and methods of activity. An analysis of the publications of S.L. Rubinstein, I.Ya. Lerner, N.N. Poddyakov, L.A. Paramonova proves that the involvement of the individual in the thought process aimed at solving some problem begins with a problem situation [3, 4, 8,]. Considering the different levels of children's preparation in creative activities, it is necessary to divide children into subgroups with "equal starting opportunities" and select a work task for them that is feasible for independent solution. Thus, in organizing individual stages of the children's activities participating in our study, we tried to find a place for setting and solving a problem, where the child can act together with the teacher, and where independently, where to follow the instructions, and where to show his own initiative. Teachers note: "When in a situation of searching for a solution to a problem, the child involves other children in a mental search, provides them with assistance in the form of instructions, explanations, questions" [12, p. 222].

The educational process in our work with children was distinguished by the fact that we built it on an activity-based basis - this, in our opinion, is the most optimal way to teach children technical skills. The activity-based approach requires transferring the child to the position of the subject of knowledge, work and communication. It is important for us that the activity of the individual, his need for self-improvement are considered not in isolation, but in the context of relationships with other people. Activity as the basis and means of education and development of the individual is emphasized in the works of A. N. Leontiev: "To master the achievements of human culture, each new generation must carry out an activity similar (though not identical) to that which stands behind these achievements" [13, p. 97].

The child's own activity in the activity is a necessary condition in the educational process and in learning. In joint activities with an adult, there are many opportunities for the child to demonstrate such activity, a creative, conscious solution to the tasks set, and not imitation or direct copying of actions. V.A. Slastenin noted that "the main provisions for organizing the pedagogical process are reflected in its principles. The principles of the pedagogical process reflect the main requirements for organizing pedagogical activity, indicate its direction, and ultimately help to creatively approach the construction of the pedagogical process" [14, p.74]. Any activity, according to V.A. Slastenin, including creative activity, in order to achieve its successful result, must be carried out at a conscious level.

Thus, in constructing the pedagogical process, we relied on the principle of the unity of knowledge, skills, consciousness and behavior, which requires the organization of activities where "... students would be convinced of the truth and vitality of the knowledge and ideas they receive, and would master the skills of social and value-based behavior" [8, p. 177]. This position entails taking into account the principle of the scientific nature of the knowledge and ideas received. Based on the laws of cognition of the environment and the development of thinking in preschool children, who think more in images than in concepts, we should rely on the visual principle of teaching children.

In primary school age, it is customary to use various types of visual aids: objects of objective reality, models, product samples, drawings, illustrations, diagrams, visual models, observations and elementary experiments, etc. N.A. Vinogradova [16] notes that many scientists

consider the principles of training and education in a single system and rely, at the same time, on the principle of taking into account the age characteristics of students, which should be taken into account in the choice of methods and means of transmitting cultural heritage to the younger generation. We take into account the principle of the child's activity in creative activity as the leading one, allowing the child to show initiative, freedom of choice of action, however, without belittling the role of the teacher, who should tactfully guide the child's activity, stimulating his cognitive and creative activity.

According to D.B. Bogoyavlenskaya [8], intellectual activity is a "psychological mechanism of higher forms of creativity". A child's intellectual activity is an integral characteristic of the personality, uniting its motivational and intellectual spheres. Mental abilities form the foundation of a child's intellectual activity. The situation in which a child is perceived as an active subject of education in preschool pedagogy is based on the principle of a personal approach.

Subjective personality traits include independence, self-discipline, self-control, self-management, purposefulness, initiative, etc., which are cultivated in early school age in the joint creative activity of a child and an adult. The principle of a personal approach to education requires that the teacher know the individual developmental characteristics of each child and take them into account in organizing various forms and types of activity and taking them into account in distributing roles, assignments, and responsibilities. This principle is closely related to the principle of democracy, which establishes equal partnership and spiritual relations between an adult and students.

A. Yu. Kozyreva defines creative tasks as "... tasks that require creative activity from students, in which the student must find a way to solve the problem himself, apply knowledge in new conditions, create something subjectively new" [11, p. 56]. Creative tasks involve the use in the creative activity of younger students mainly of methods based on intuitive procedures (such as the method of enumerating options, analogy, etc.). Modeling, resource approach, and some fantasy techniques are actively used. Based on the analysis of the literature by authors G.S. Altshuller, V.A. Bukhvalov, A.A. Gin, M.A. Danilov, A.M. Matyushkin and others, the following requirements can be identified for the development of creative tasks: - openness (content of the problem situation or contradiction); - compliance of the conditions with the selected creative methods; - possibility of different solutions; - taking into account the current level of development; - taking into account the age characteristics of students.

Taking these requirements into account, it is possible to construct a whole cycle of creative tasks aimed at developing individual components of creative activity. It is important not only to provide this system of creative tasks in lessons, but also to organize its natural transition of younger students from artistic creativity to perception and return with a baggage of impressions and knowledge again to independent creativity. According to V.A. Levin [11], the system of creative tasks includes such components as target, activity, content and result.

The system-forming factor is the personality of the student: his goals, abilities, needs, motives, and many other individual psychological characteristics, as well as subjective creative experience. When selecting the content for the system of creative assignments in lessons, it is necessary to take into account the fact that the creative activity of younger students is carried out, mainly, on problems already solved by society. It should be noted that in choosing lessons in which the teacher organizes the creative activity of students, a measure is needed. Students get used to unusual ways of working, lose interest in reproductive methods of assimilation of material, which

require memorization, awareness of the material, the method of performing actions, academic performance noticeably decreases. The place of creative lessons in the general system should be determined by the teacher himself depending on the specific situation, the conditions of the content of the material and the individual characteristics of the teacher himself.

It should be noted that lessons with episodic creative activity are ineffective, they will not lead to the development of a creative attitude to work, the desire for invention and rationalization, experimental and research work, i.e. to the development of creative qualities of the individual. A strictly thought-out system is needed in developing a strategy for working with children to develop creative activity. In organizing creative activity, it is necessary to carefully select the forms of organizing children. In a technology lesson, it is possible to organize frontal, group and individual forms of educational work. Each lesson has its own structure, consisting of several stages: learning new material, consolidating knowledge, checking knowledge, skills, abilities, generalization and systematization of knowledge, homework.

The ratio of the lesson stages depends on the content, didactic and cognitive objectives of the lesson, the choice of methods and the use of technical teaching aids. Thus, in the process of creative activity, the student develops intellectually and emotionally, determines his or her attitude to life and his or her place in it, gains experience in collective interaction, and improves the skills of working with various tools and materials. It is obvious that in educational activity, the elements of students' creativity are manifested, first of all, in the peculiarities of its course; namely: in the ability to see a problem, to find new ways of solving specific practical and educational tasks in non-standard situations. Continuous, systematic creative activity of students throughout all years of study at school will certainly lead to the development of a sustainable interest in creativity.

In this regard, the role of the school in educating active, proactive, creatively thinking people is increasing. To achieve this goal, it is necessary to purposefully organize the creative activities of students in primary school. The creative nature of man is manifested in intellectual activity. The teacher in the "Technology" lessons encourages the child to be intellectually active by the fact that the material is accessible, and the origami technique itself is based on a set of already existing intellectual abilities, but different from those required, for example, to compose poetry, paint pictures. The accessibility of the presentation of the material in the lessons has a positive effect on the intellectual activity of children. In psychology, one can distinguish children who are kinesthetic, who need to touch everything, and there are most of them.

There are visual learners, they need to see everything. And there are auditory learners, they need to hear everything. But most children of primary school age have manual intelligence and are very interested in learning about the world through manual labor, tactile perception of new types of materials, shapes, sizes, etc. Thus, the choice of origami work in the Technology lessons is a vivid example of the fact that paper can be touched, bent, cut out, drawn on. Origami technique has the ability to show the image of an animal, flower, structure, etc. It also gives the child the opportunity to recreate his product, while getting to know the purpose, the history of this or that object that he created.

Origami technique has the ability to awaken intellectual activity, i.e. the creative ability of a child. The task of primary school teachers is to care for the moral education of children, their physical and mental development, the education of diligence, the development of abilities, aesthetic gifts. A teacher at school deals, first of all, with the integral personality of a child. Each is interesting in his or her uniqueness, and the high task of pedagogy is to preserve this uniqueness,

to grow a valuable personality, to develop inclinations and talents, to expand the possibilities of each child.

According to N.M. Akchurina-Muftieva, the main problem a person faces during their life is “how to realize themselves, how to use hidden talents and abilities. Everyone has talents and abilities, but not everyone realizes them. The question is how to awaken abilities for life and how to help them develop. One of the ways to optimize the educational process and the full development of a child’s personality is to organize technology lessons. Labor lessons help a child realize themselves, use their talents and abilities” [2, p.56]. Early identification of children’s creative inclinations and abilities is of great importance. This allows for the maximum use of all opportunities for developing a child’s creative potential.

As Ya. A. Ponomarev writes: “in the process of education, the need for self-change is formed, the created conditions and the developing environment of the class, school contribute to the maximum development of the inclinations and abilities of each child, the formation of talents, the development of a spiritually rich personality, capable of making non-standard decisions” [14, p. 375]. One of the favorite types of creative activity for children is origami. Origami in our country is known as the art of paper plasticity, born in Japan. In Japanese, “ori” means folded instantly, and “gami” means divine paper [3]. The art of folding has been known since ancient times, soon after the invention and widespread use of paper, just as in every culture the customs of folding fabric are known and widespread (eastern turbans, Greek tunics and Indian saris, Spanish collars, bows and other decorations).

Therefore, researchers of creativity associate paper folding with universal human natural needs and interests, “... although, of course, it is influenced by the culture, customs and circumstances of a specific person-folder” [2, p.101]. In the East, the square (the canonical form of the origami blank) has always been treated with respect. The idea of turning a square of paper into an image was quite natural for the Japanese, accustomed to the square shape of many things, starting with the hieroglyph. In ancient China, the square symbolized the earth and the cosmos, with which it merges into one. All games born in Buddhist countries also have the shape of a square: chess, go, tangram. In the Buddhist view, all things are in a state of interpenetration, everything is connected in everything. Therefore, the square as the basis of the universe should be able to flow into thousands of forms [2].

In our country, origami was presented as an activity on making paper crafts, and this technique was taught in labor lessons or in special clubs in institutions of additional education. The creation of works in the origami technique is classified as a type of artistic design. The study of the development of the art of paper folding allowed teachers to identify three directions of folding techniques over time. The first direction is origami folded in the traditional manner from a square, without cuts. Origami of this direction is distinguished by high complexity of execution. To fold a product from a whole square, even an advanced master in this technique needs to spend several hours. Kawasaki roses made from folds are famous in this technique.

Nowadays origami masters have learned to convey the resemblance to an object by making as few folds as possible on a square blank [2]. The second direction is models folded from a regular triangle and half a square, torn vertically or diagonally, from five, six, and octagons, or simply from a sheet of standard-sized writing paper. Such products are mostly practiced in our country. Models in this direction represent a prefabricated product reminiscent of the macrame technique.

The third direction is the composition of models from two, three, four, etc. identical parts - modules.

The technique of construction, which uses not only paper folding, but also cutting in different directions, is called kirigami. One of the ways to obtain paper figures using the kirigami technique consists of the ability to fold a sheet of paper in half and cut out the desired silhouette. In this way, three-dimensional figures for tabletop theater, masks, toys, and souvenirs are obtained [9]. In European pedagogy, the great potential for developing a child's personality through paper construction was revealed by the German educator Friedrich Froebel. Froebel believed that life, movement, and knowledge are three parts of a single harmonious chord, so the manual labor that Froebel involved his students in was not aimed at training a craftsman, but at training a more perfect person. He proposed studying the basics of geometry not with a ruler, compass, and abstract concepts, but through the literally tangible realities of folding paper [7]. In Russian pedagogical practice, origami was practiced by L. N. Tolstoy. The writer recognized the art of paper folding, believing that this art has great developmental potential.

In modern teaching, teaching individual elements of origami is provided for in some programs for modern primary schools, the most common use of the manual by V.V. Vygonov "Primary School: Labor Training. Crafts, Models, Toys" [10], but the manual focuses on the development of mathematical concepts and provides a series of tasks in mathematics using origami. Basically, teaching origami in domestic school pedagogy is aimed at developing fine muscles of the fingers and improving paper handling skills. However, the task of developing spatial thinking of schoolchildren in origami classes is becoming increasingly relevant. The ability to examine an object from different points of view and highlight its features is fundamental in solving geometric and practical problems.

Thus, the "Technology" lessons using origami contribute to the development of creative abilities in younger students, helping to initiate the child's intellectual activity as the basis for creative abilities. For the successful development of creative abilities in the "Technology" lessons, the following conditions are necessary: - a specially developed program of lessons in the origami technique, which is aimed at developing creative abilities in younger students; - the lesson structure should include moments of improvisation, original additions for the final completion of the product image from the child's side; - to stimulate creative competition and demand for students' work, exhibitions and competitions of children's work are organized; - during lessons, children act as creators, co-authors, critics, evaluating their creative product, as well as the work of other children; - the teacher acts as an assistant who will always support the initiative and correct the student's actions, if necessary, so that the product started is always completed. Origami always arouses children's interest and gives them great creative pleasure in a pedagogically appropriate organized activity, which is an effective means of developing the creative abilities of younger students.

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